

This may be attributed to the formation of $(R-C_6H_4S)^+$ (IV), a possible mechanistic rationalisation for the formation of which is given below^{8a} (Scheme 2).

Other prominent peaks observed are due to the loss of OH, H₂O and COOH as is evidenced in the case of acids. Peaks at *m/e* 132 and 131 are observed in all the thioureas by loss of ArNH and ArNH₂, respectively from the molecular ions. Peaks of moderate intensity corresponding to the ion $(R-C_6H_4-N-C=O)^+$ were observed in the case of all the thioureas. The formation of this ion may be rationalised by the breaking of 2-3 and 4-5 bonds of a 3-substituted-2-thio-dihydrouracil (V) which might have been formed by the loss of water molecule from the parent ion.

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Effect of Substituents on Chromatographic Behaviour of Imines

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MOST organic compounds have been studied by thin layer chromatography¹. However, no systematic study²⁻⁴ on the tlc of the imines⁵ has been made so far. This communication describes the tlc of 21 imines using methanol-H₂SO₄ (95 : 5 v/v) as spraying reagent and the effect of substituents on the R_f values of the imines. The results of this study are at variance with those reported earlier².

Experimental

Benzal anilines, *p*-chlorobenzal anilines and *p*-methoxybenzal anilines were prepared by condensing aniline and substituted anilines with benzaldehyde, *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde and anisaldehyde, respectively.

Silica gel G (Polypharm., Bombay, 100 g) and water (200 ml) was stirred thoroughly to give a fine slurry. The mixture was then coated on glass plates (20 × 5 cm) to a thickness of about 0.10 cm. The plates were air dried (15 min) and activated for 4 hr at 120° in an oven. Sample solutions were prepared in methanol and applied with fine capillaries on the activated plates. The plates were developed in glass chambers with ground in lids by ascending technique for 20 min. The developed plates were air dried, sprayed with methanol-sulphuric acid mixture (95 : 5 v/v) and heated in an oven till the spots were clearly discernible.

Results and Discussion

The highest R_f values were obtained from benzene-methanol (1 : 1), but the resolution was poor. Benzene showed a high resolving capability, but the best results were obtained in benzene-ethylacetate (95 : 5) for most of the imines. R_f values of the imines were found to be independent of the plate size.

The effect of substitution in C-phenyl ring/N-phenyl ring on the R_f values was studied by comparing the values of substituted imine with those of imine of the unsubstituted benzaldehyde/aniline. It was observed that the presence of electron donor groups (CH₃, OCH₃, OC₂H₅, etc.) in the N-phenyl ring decreased the R_f values whereas electron withdrawing substituents (Cl, Br, NO₂) increased the values. These results are at variance with the earlier reported results². Regarding substitution in C-phenyl ring, both Cl and OCH₃ group in *p*-position showed an increase in the R_f values (Table 1).

TABLE 1— R_f VALUES OF IMINES IN BENZENE-ETHYLACETATE (95 : 5)

Sl. No.	Substituent in C-phenyl ring	Substituent in N-phenyl ring	Colour with spraying reagent	R_f
1.	H	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	Gray	0.22
2.	H	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	Light pink	0.23
3.	H	<i>p</i> -OH ₂	Yellow	0.27
4.	H	H	Blue	0.28
5.	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	Yellow	0.31
6.	H	<i>p</i> -Br	Brown	0.41
7.	H	<i>p</i> -Cl	Light brown	0.46
8.	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	Violet	0.20
9.	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	Violet	0.21
10.	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	Light orange	0.36
11.	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	<i>p</i> -OH ₂	Yellow	0.39
12.	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	H	Yellowish green	0.41
13.	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	<i>p</i> -Br	Yellow	0.46
14.	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	<i>p</i> -Cl	Light yellow	0.48
15.	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	Violet	0.27
16.	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	Violet	0.27
17.	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -OH ₂	Light brown	0.39
18.	<i>p</i> -Cl	H	Blue	0.42
19.	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	Yellow	0.44
20.	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Br	Yellow	0.87
21.	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Cl	Light yellow	0.90

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Benzohydroxamic Acid as an Indicator in the Titrimetric Determination of

Alkali-Earth Metals

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HYDROXAMIC acids are widely used as chelating agents for metals¹⁻³. They form coloured complexes with vanadium, titanium, molybdenum, etc⁴⁻⁵. Complexation and gravimetric estimation of the alkali earth metals with hydroxamic acids are reported but they do not give any colour⁶⁻⁸ and the hydroxamic acids have not so far been used as an indicator for the determination of alkali earth metals. In the present investigation, benzohydroxamic acid (BHA) has been used as an indicator for direct titrimetric determination of beryllium, magnesium and calcium. These are determined in presence of each other and several other metal ions.

It is well known that EDTA forms strong complexes with beryllium, magnesium, calcium and iron(III). The fact that iron(III) forms violet

coloured stable complexes with hydroxamic acids has been utilized for titrimetric determination of alkali earth ions. At first the alkali earth ions are complexed with excess EDTA, the excess EDTA is titrated with iron(III) and the excess iron(III) is immediately indicated by the formation of violet reddish brown colour with BHA. Hence, the equivalent amount of metal ion can be determined by back calculation.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of B.D.H., AnalaR or E. Merck, G.R. grades unless otherwise stated.

Metal ion solutions: Standard solutions of beryllium as BeSO₄·4H₂O, magnesium as MgSO₄·7H₂O and calcium as CaNO₃ were prepared by dissolving the requisite amount in distilled water and standardized volumetrically⁹. Standard 0.01 M iron(III) solution was prepared by dissolving the requisite amount of ferric ammonium sulphate and standardized volumetrically⁹.

EDTA: Standard 0.01 M EDTA disodium solution was prepared by dissolving the requisite amount of disodium EDTA (G.R., E. Merck).

Benzohydroxamic acid: Benzohydroxamic acid was synthesized as described by Agrawal *et al*¹⁰ and directly used as indicator for the titrimetric determination of the alkali earth (Be, Mg and Ca).

Procedure:

In a 250 ml conical flask an aliquot of metal ion solution is transferred and an excess of EDTA (two times the required amount) is added. It is heated upto boiling. After cooling, the pH is adjusted for each metal, and 0.1 g benzohydroxamic acid is added as indicator. It is titrated against standard iron(III) solution to a violet brown red end point.

Results and Discussion

Beryllium:

Beryllium (0.1-5.0 mg) is mixed with standard EDTA solution and titrated in acidic media (0.5-0.8 M HCl) in presence of KCl solution (10 ml of 5%). The end point is indicated by a change from light yellow to red brown colour. The results are shown in Table 1.

Effect of diverse ions: Beryllium could be easily titrated in presence of Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Sr²⁺ and Ba²⁺ in acidic media since these metals form the complexes in alkaline media. Beryllium could be titrated in presence of Cd²⁺, Ti⁴⁺, Ni²⁺, Hg²⁺, UO₂²⁺, Ce⁴⁺, Mn²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Al³⁺ with the addition of tartaric acid and tartrate.

Magnesium:

Magnesium (0.1-5.0 mg) is mixed with standard EDTA solution, the pH is adjusted to 9-10 with ammonium hydroxide (0.1 M) and ammonium chloride (0.1 M) and titrated with standard iron(III) using benzohydroxamic acid as an indicator. The